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Resonance observation of pump-turbine runners from the stationary frame: analytical-numerical model for the natural mode splitting of submerged rotating disc-blades-disc structures

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ABSTRACT

With the growing adoption of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power, pumped storage technology is flourishing in several developing countries. Based on the widespread vibration issues faced by pumped storage units, particularly in their runners and top covers, this paper aims to investigate the natural mode splitting of complex rotating structures and the observation of this phenomenon from the stationary reference frame.

The finite element method (FEM) is employed to analyze the characteristics of the diametrical mode shape of a disc-blades-disc (DBD) structure, which is representative of pumped turbine runners. An analytical approach is utilized to investigate the formation mechanism of these diametrical components, thereby predicting the rules governing the mode shape splitting of underwater rotating structures. The imposed modal motion method, based on computational fluid dynamics (CFD), is used to predict the natural frequency splitting and hydraulic damping splitting of the DBD structure. Building on these studies, a combined approach of analytical methods, CFD, and FEM is employed to predict the resonance characteristics of the rotating structure on the stationary reference frame, as well as the resulting pressure pulsations and the vibrations of the stationary casing.

Results reveal that the relationship between the diametrical components of the natural modes of the DBD structure is strictly related to the number of blades. When the structure rotates in water, its diametrical modes split into two independent travelling wave modes, each containing multiple diametrical components (i.e., travelling wave components), with the difference between these components equaling the number of blades. The model predicts that if a travelling wave mode is excited, a 'multi-frequency' feature, with frequency differences equal to the product of the number of blades and the rotational frequency, will be observed on the stationary frame. These findings are consistent with the multi-frequency vibration phenomena observed in some real cases, providing a foundation for further understanding the vibration mechanisms in pump-turbines and similar mechanical structures.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, renewable energy sources, particularly wind and solar power, have seen rapid growth worldwide [1,2]. Due to the strong intermittency of both wind and solar power, their large-scale integration presents significant challenges to the grid's capacity and stability [3]. To address this, the construction of supporting energy storage facilities is considered the most effective solution. Among these, pumped storage is the most mature, cost-effective, and scalable energy storage technology. As a result, the role of pumped storage plants in grid regulation is becoming increasingly crucial [4].

One of the key equipment in pumped storage plants is the pump-turbine runner which converts hydraulic energy into mechanical energy when operating the unit as a turbine and in the other way around when storing electrical energy in form of potential energy.

The safe and stable operation of the pump-turbine runners is essential to guarantee the correct functioning of the plant. Nevertheless, pump-turbine runners are subjected to extremely high loads because they usually operate with high heads on one side, while on the other side, their structure is designed with far fewer blades than conventional Francis runners. In fact, to avoid adverse commercial repercussions, most stability issues have not been publicly reported. Nevertheless, in some cases academics and researchers from industry have reported problems, such as cracking of the runner and stationary components, as well as excessive vibrations in the rotating structures as well on the stationary components [5–9]. The runner, being the core component of the pump-turbine, faces particularly severe challenges, with its damage having particularly detrimental consequences [5,7,8]. Therefore, in-depth study of the vibration characteristics of pump-turbine runners is of significant importance for the design and operational management of these units.

Fig. 1 shows the abnormal vibration behavior characteristic (time–frequency plane) observed in a 250 MW pumped storage unit in China with 9 blades and a rotational speed of 333 rpm. The measured vibration levels were abnormally high. A sensor was measuring the vibration from the head cover (stationary frame) under partial load conditions. In that case a multi-frequency vibration phenomena was clearly detected with vibrations at frequencies 100.7 Hz, 150.7 Hz, 200.7 Hz, and 250.7 Hz. Among these, 150.7 Hz was the dominant frequency, and the operating deflection shape (ODS) analysis indicated a 4 nodal diameter mode. The secondary dominant frequency, 200.7 Hz, corresponded to a 5 nodal diameter mode. During start-up and shutdown, the frequency of the abnormal top cover vibrations varied with the rotational speed, but the frequency differences always corresponded to the blade passing frequency. After a thorough analysis of the experimental results, we believe this distinctive multi-frequency vibration is a manifestation of resonance transmission from the runner to the top cover. This paper aims to investigate the underlying mechanisms of this phenomenon.

In order to investigate this complex vibration phenomenon which may shows a resonant behavior of the pump turbine runner, it is necessary to discuss first about modal parameters. The modal parameters of a structural system, including frequency, mode shape, and damping, determine its dynamic response under specific excitation forces, and provide a foundation for resonance prediction and mechanism analysis. It is well known that when a runner and its simplified structure are submerged in a heavy fluid, such as water, their modal frequencies are significantly lower compared to those in air, while modal damping increases substantially. The inertial forces exerted by the fluid on the structure (i.e., added mass) and hydraulic damping are the primary causes of the differences between the dry and wet modal characteristics of the structure. Numerous scholars have studied the effects of factors such as fluid density, cavitation, flow velocity, and wall proximity on the added mass and hydraulic damping of the runner and its simplified structure [10]. For example, in terms of flow velocity, De La Torre et al. [11] conducted experimental studies on the natural frequency of a NACA 0009 hydrofoil in flowing water. The results showed that at higher flow velocities and smaller attack angles, the added mass was relatively small, but the change was not significant. Compared to still water, the natural frequency variation of the hydrofoil in flowing water was approximately 3%. Additionally, extensive experimental research has shown that, within lower flow velocity ranges, the hydraulic damping of structures such as hydrofoils [12,13] and grids [14] remains nearly constant as the flow velocity increases. Yao et al. [12] first proposed the concept that hydraulic damping remains constant before the resonance velocity and then increases linearly with flow velocity after the resonance velocity, a view later confirmed by Bergan et al. [14]. Another key factor influencing modal parameters is the wall reflection of pressure waves. Typically, the closer a submerged structure is to the wall, the more pronounced the added mass effect, leading to a lower natural frequency [15]. Askari et al. [16] studied the impact of axial and radial gaps on the modal frequencies of a disc in a tank, pointing out that because the dynamic displacement of the disc is mainly axial, the added mass is more sensitive to

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the multi-frequency abnormal vibration observed in a pump-turbine from a vibration sensor on the head cover.

the axial gap. Experimental studies on submerged discs by Moraga et al. [17] showed that hydraulic damping increased significantly as rigid walls approached. Furthermore, the effects of factors such as mode shapes and amplitudes on damping vary under different wall proximity conditions. Currently, there is limited research directly focused on the modal characteristics of complex runners. Based on existing studies on the modal characteristics of complex runners [18–20], the observed trends align closely with those of simpler structures.

In early studies, it was generally assumed that the effect of rotation on the modal characteristics of hydraulic machinery runners is minimal, due to the relatively low rotational speed and high stiffness, and thus this effect was often neglected [21]. However, if the relative rotation between a disc-shaped structure and the surrounding heavy fluid is considered, a special resonance mechanism is triggered. This mechanism, first proposed by Kubota and Ohashi [22], suggests that the diametrical mode splits from its original standing wave into two counter-propagating travelling waves, corresponding to two distinct frequencies. It is important to note that this result is observed from the rotating coordinate system. Later, Presas et al. [23–25] experimentally validated this phenomenon, observing significant splitting and slight drift in the diametrical mode of a rotating disc in a casing from the rotating reference frame. In their recent research, Louyot et al. [26] used theoretical analysis to reveal the mechanisms behind the frequency splitting and drift, where the linear and quadratic dependencies of the added mass on the relative circumferential velocity between the disturbance wave and the fluid rotation lead to these effects. After mode splitting, in addition to changes in added mass and natural frequency, the damping of the two travelling wave modes may also no longer be identical. In experimental tests, when Presas et al. [27] applied frequency sweeping excitation to a rotating disc, they found noticeable differences in the resonance amplitudes of the two travelling wave modes with the same diametrical number. Specifically, the forward travelling wave mode (in the direction of disc rotation) had a smaller amplitude, while the backward travelling wave mode had a larger amplitude, indirectly reflecting the relative damping characteristics of the forward and backward travelling wave modes.

In addition to experimental methods, the phenomenon of mode splitting can also be studied through numerical simulations. Presas et al. [23,28] were the first to use an acoustic-structure coupling method to compute the natural frequencies of an experimental disc. However, that acoustic-structure coupling method may not be suitable for complex DBD structures, which consist of rotor discs and blades [29]. To address this issue, Louyot et al. [26] developed a method similar to bidirectional fluid–structure coupling using user-defined functions in Ansys CFX and Fortran subroutines [30]. They compared the frequency splitting results obtained from numerical simulations with experimental data, verifying the accuracy of this numerical approach. In theory, this method could be used to simulate DBD structures, but ensuring the efficiency and stability of the solution remains a challenge due to the coupling between the flow field and the structural discretization equations based on the Runge-Kutta method. For complex geometries, an imposed modal motion method [31,32] appears more promising, as it offers higher efficiency and stability. In recent research, Xia et al. [32] used the imposed modal motion method to analyze the impact of wall distance on the mode splitting of a rotating disc in water, and the results showed a good agreement with the experimental trends observed.

In fact, the modal characteristics of runners are more complex than those of discs. To investigate this, Presas et al. [29] designed a DBD assembly and conducted experimental modal analysis in air. The results showed that the mode shape of the assembly contained multiple diametrical components, in contrast to the diametrical mode shape of simple discs, which can be fully described by a single diametrical component. Additionally, due to the presence of several diametrical components for each diametrical mode shape, when the rotating DBD assembly resonates in a certain vibration mode shape, several frequency peaks can be observed in the stationary reference frame. This phenomenon is somewhat related to the multi-frequency vibration of the top cover observed in the real case depicted in Fig. 1, but does not fully match, as the mode splitting that occurs when the structure rotates in water has not been considered. Previously, similar rotating blade-disc coupling systems [33–35] had been extensively studied, but these investigations were almost rooted in the context of gas turbomachinery. Consequently, the influence of relative rotation between a heavy fluid, such as water, and the discs was generally overlooked, and little attention was paid to the distinct frequency features observed in different reference frames.

Fig. 2. Research object. (a) photograph of the DBD structure; (b) connection between the blade and the disc; (c) casing filled with water.

Building on the background outlined above, this paper aims to conduct a numerical modal study of the DBD structure designed by Presas et al. [29]. First, finite element analysis is performed to examine the modal parameters of the non-rotating structure in both air and still water, with a particular focus on the composition of diametrical components. Then, an analytical approach is used to investigate the mechanism behind the formation of diametrical components and to explore the splitting rules of mode shapes for the underwater rotating structure. Based on this, a simulation model for imposed modal motion is developed, tailored for the structure, to predict changes in the modal parameters when the structure rotates in water. Finally, by combining the analytical methods, CFD, and FEM techniques described in this paper, the resonant vibration response of the rotating structure in the stationary reference frame, including pressure pulsations and vibrations of stationary components, is predicted.

2. Modal characteristics of the non-rotating disc-blades-disc structure

This chapter aims to solve the modal parameters of the non-rotating structure in both air and still water using FEM, with a focus on investigating the composition of the diametrical components in each mode of the DBD structure. The results will provide valuable insights into the modal characteristics of pump-turbine runners, serving as a reference for further analytical analysis and mode splitting calculations in the subsequent sections.

2.1. Research object

In previous studies, Presas et al. [29] designed the DBD structure shown in Fig. 2(a). The structure is primarily made of structural steel and consists of two circular discs with an outer diameter of 200 mm, an inner diameter of 20 mm, and a thickness of 3 mm, along with seven flat plates measuring $173 \times 22 \times 4$ mm. The inner side of the discs is fixed to the shaft, while the blades are welded between the two discs. The connection between the blades and the discs can be modelled as three welding points, each measuring $10 \times 4 \times 1$ mm, located as shown in Fig. 2(b).

To further investigate the dynamic characteristics of the structure in water, it is placed within a cylindrical closed casing as shown in Fig. 2(c), which is filled with water. The cylindrical casing is fixed at its outer surface, with an outer diameter of 250 mm and a height of 74 mm. The wall thickness of the casing is 20 mm at the top and sides, and 6 mm at the bottom. The structure is centrally positioned, with an axial clearance of 10 mm and a radial clearance of 5 mm from the casing.

As we will discuss later, the design of this DBD structure was made with the purpose of imitating the diametrical mode shapes characteristics of a pump-turbine runner.

2.2. Governing equations

For the inherent modes of submerged structures, the acoustical-structural coupling method is commonly employed for numerical prediction in engineering. This method has been extensively validated. For example, Egusquiza et al. [8,36,37] applied this approach to determine the natural frequencies of a turbine in a water tank, with results that closely matched experimental data. Furthermore, Rodriguez et al. [38] conducted studies on a flat plate in water, further demonstrating that the acoustical-structural coupling method can accurately predict the effects of rigid walls on added mass and natural frequency.

In the acoustical-structural coupling model, the fluid domain is discretized using acoustic elements. Assuming that the fluid is compressible, irrotational, free from body forces, and has no mean flow. After a series of derivations, the discretized acoustic wave equation can be obtained [39]:

$$[M_F] \left\{ \ddot{p}_e \right\} + [C_F] \left\{ \dot{p}_e \right\} + [K_F] \{p_e\} + \rho [R]^T \{\ddot{u}\} = \{F_F\} \quad (1)$$

where $[M_F]$, $[C_F]$, and $[K_F]$ represent the mass matrix, damping matrix, and stiffness matrix of the acoustic fluid, respectively; $\{p_e\}$ is the pressure vector on the element; ρ is the constant density of the acoustic fluid; $[R]^T$ is the boundary matrix of the fluid; and $\{F_F\}$ is the acoustic fluid load.

On the other hand, for linear structural dynamic systems, the governing equation, after finite element discretization, can be expressed as:

$$[M_S] \{\ddot{u}\} + [C_S] \{\dot{u}\} + [K_S] \{u\} = \{F_S\} \quad (2)$$

here, $[M_S]$, $[C_S]$, and $[K_S]$ represent the mass matrix, damping matrix, and stiffness matrix of the structure, respectively; $\{u\}$ is the nodal displacement vector, and $\{F_S\}$ is the external excitation force vector.

To fully describe the fluid-structure interaction problem, the fluid pressure load acting on the coupling surface $\{F^{pr}\}$ must also be considered:

$$[M_S] \{\ddot{u}\} + [C_S] \{\dot{u}\} + [K_S] \{u\} = \{F_S\} + \{F^{pr}\} \quad (3)$$

$$\{F^{pr}\} = \iint_{\Gamma_I} \{N\} p_F n ds = \iint_{\Gamma_I} \{N\} \{N\}^T \{n\} ds \{p_e\} = [R] \{p_e\} \quad (4)$$

In which, $[M_S]$, $[C_S]$, and $[K_S]$ represent the mass matrix, damping matrix, and stiffness matrix of the structure, respectively. $\{F_S\}$ represents the external loads applied to the structure.

By combining Equation (1) and Equation (3), the complete discretized acoustical-structural coupling equation can be obtained:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [M_S] & 0 \\ \rho_0 [R]^T & [M_F] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\ddot{u}\} \\ \{\dot{p}_e\} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} [C_S] & 0 \\ 0 & [C_F] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\dot{u}\} \\ \{\dot{p}_e\} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} [K_S] & -[R] \\ 0 & [K_F] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{u\} \\ \{p_e\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F_S\} \\ \{F_F\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The detailed derivation of the above equation can be found in reference [36].

2.3. Finite element model

An acoustic-structure coupling model for the DBD structure and the surrounding fluid was established using ANSYS®. In the structure, the density of the blade and disc is 7850 kg/m³, with an elastic modulus of 200 GPa; the density of the weld points is the same, while the elastic modulus is set to 2 GPa. The density of the water is 997 kg/m³, and the sound speed is 1482 m/s. Fixed constraints are applied to the inner side of the disc, and the interface between the fluid domain and the structure is defined as the fluid-structure coupling surface, with the outer boundary of the fluid domain set as a fully reflective wall.

The structural domain and fluid domain are discretized using high-order elements Solid 187 and Fluid 221, respectively. Four mesh sets are created with specific ratios, and the total number of nodes is 147,485, 307,309, 733,886, and 1,532,494. The first four natural frequencies of the underwater DBD structure calculated with these mesh sets are shown in Fig. 3. It can be observed that as the total number of mesh nodes increases, the results tend to converge. Since the computational load involved in this analysis is not large, the mesh with a total of 1,532,494 nodes is selected for subsequent analysis. When calculating the modes of the structure in air, the fluid domain can be suppressed.

2.4. Results and Discussion

The natural modes of the DBD structure were solved for both air and still water, and the frequencies and displacement contour plots of the low-order modes are presented in Table 1. Similar to other disc-like structures, such as high-head Francis turbines [15], the low-order modes of this structure also exhibit axial-dominated mode shapes with varying numbers of nodal diameters. In certain modes, the two discs vibrate in phase (IP); in other modes, the two discs vibrate out of phase or counterphase (CP). Based on the characteristics observed in the displacement contour plots, the modes are temporarily named as “n ND-IP” or “n ND-CP,” where n refers to the number of nodal diameters observed visually. Nevertheless, as it is discussed in this paper this concept of nodal diameters needs to be further developed and clarified for DBD structures.

The simulated natural frequencies were compared with the experimental results of the structure in air [29]. The results indicate that the error in the higher-order modes is relatively large, with the maximum error being only 5.50 %, which is acceptable.

Due to the small gap between the structure and the wall, the added mass effect of the water is significant, leading to a substantial decrease in the natural frequencies of the structure underwater compared to those in air. It is evident that the frequency decrease varies across different modes. To quantify the added mass effect of the water, the added mass coefficient is introduced:

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{f_a - \text{SIM}}{f_w - \text{SIM}} \right)^2 - 1 \quad (6)$$

The added mass coefficients corresponding to different modes are shown in the Fig. 4. By categorizing each mode according to “IP” and “CP” and arranging them by the number of nodal diameters, it can be observed that: for both “IP” and “CP” modes, the larger the nodal

Fig. 3. Mesh sensitivity analysis of the acoustic-structure coupling model.

Table 1
Simulation results of the low-order modes of the DBD structure in air and still water.

Mode shapes	1ND-IP	2ND-IP	0ND-IP	3ND-IP	3ND-CP	2ND-CP	4ND-IP	1ND-CP
Contour plots 								
f_{a-SIM} [Hz]	294.62	305.52	312.24	333.41	347.47	446.47	566.74	569.93
f_{a-EXP} [Hz]	\	303.10	\	326.33	\	428.95	\	540.22
Error [%]	\	0.80	\	2.17	\	4.08	\	5.50
f_{w-SIM} [Hz]	90.81	115.06	75.92	146.76	109.71	136.98	274.53	159.16

Fig. 4. Added mass coefficients corresponding to each mode for the DBD structure tested.

diameter number, the smaller the added mass. Additionally, for the same number of nodal diameters, the added mass for the “CP” mode is larger than that for the “IP” mode, with the difference becoming more significant as the nodal diameter number increases.

The following presents an analysis of the mode shapes. It should be noted that the current conventional method in the field of hydraulic machinery defines the mode shapes of disc-like structures based on the number of nodal diameters observed visually and uses this information to determine whether a resonance on the runner can be triggered. Basically, it is assumed, that if the rotor–stator interaction frequency matches one of the natural frequencies of the structure and the excitation shape (mainly defined by the number of guide vanes and rotating blades) corresponds to the structural mode shape, the resonance will occur. This was experimentally demonstrated by Presas et al. [40], but for simple disk structures. However, with a deeper understanding of the inherent modal characteristics of DBD structures, which are much more representative for real pump-turbine runners, it becomes apparent that this definition method is inaccurate.

Essentially, a nodal diameter is a line formed by the nodal points or zeros of the waves propagating along the circumference. The number of nodal diameters numerically corresponds to the wave number of a circumferential travelling wave or standing wave. For a simple disc, each mode corresponds to a single circumferential wave, which can be seen as a sine wave, as shown in Fig. 5(a). However, for a DBD structure or turbine runner, the interference from the blades results in the formation of multiple waves with different wavelengths, as shown in Fig. 5(b) to (i). Therefore, each mode of the structure or turbine runner contains multiple diametrical components.

Presas et al. [29] proposed a method for identifying the diametrical components within complex mode shapes by performing a Fourier series expansion of the outer edge deformation. Fig. 5 presents the results obtained using this method. For the structure in question, the diametrical components and corresponding amplitudes of the upper and lower discs in any given mode are nearly identical. But the diametrical components and corresponding amplitudes differ between modes. A preliminary analysis shows a specific relationship between the diametrical components and the number of blades, Z_b . For this 7-bladed structure, if a mode contains diametrical component n , it will necessarily also contain diametrical components $|n - 7|$ and $|n + 7|$. For example, in the 2ND-IP mode shown in Fig. 5(c), the mode contains a series of diametrical components, including 2, 5, 9, 12, 16, etc. However, the components with values greater than 5 have very small amplitudes and can be ignored. For any given mode of the structure, the dominant amplitudes primarily come from the first two diametrical components. The component with the largest amplitude is referred to as the dominant diametrical component, while the next largest is termed the sub-dominant diametrical component.

To further analyze the distribution of the amplitudes of the diametrical components, the proportion of the amplitude of the dominant diametrical component in each mode was extracted and is presented in Fig. 6. Overall, the closer the values of the dominant

Fig. 5. Diametrical components in each mode. (a) 3ND mode of simple disc; (b)-(i) Modes of DBD structure: (b) 1ND-IP; (c) 2ND-IP; (d) 0ND-IP; (e) 3ND-IP; (f) 3ND-CP; (g) 2ND-CP; (h) 4ND-IP; (i) 1ND-CP.

Fig. 6. Proportion of the amplitude of the dominant diametrical component in each mode.

diametrical component and the sub-dominant diametrical component, the closer their corresponding amplitudes are, which leads to a lower proportion of the dominant diametrical component’s amplitude. Specifically, for the “CP” modes, the proportion of the dominant diametrical component’s amplitude is very low, close to 0.5. On the other hand, for the “IP” modes, the proportion of the dominant diametrical component’s amplitude is relatively higher, ranging from 0.61 to 0.84. When the value of the dominant diametrical component, n_d , is less than $Z_b/2$, the larger n_d is, the smaller the corresponding amplitude becomes. For $n_d > Z_b/2$, only the 4ND-IP mode has been captured, and its pattern remains unclear.

It is worth noting that, due to the comparable amplitudes of the dominant and sub-dominant diametrical components, when performing resonance assessment of DBD structures (i.e. pump-turbine runners), it is necessary to consider the vibration avoidance margin of the sub-dominant diametrical component in certain modes. For instance, in the case of a pump turbine with 9 blades and 22 guide vanes, the vibration mode of the rotor–stator interference pressure field is mainly characterized by an excitation of $n = 4$, and the excitation frequency in the rotating reference frame is 22 times the rotational frequency [7]. According to current industry standards, it is only required that the structural natural frequency of the runner’s 4ND mode avoids the 22 times the rotational frequency. However, the 5ND mode of this runner is likely to contain a significant diametrical component 4, meaning that the natural frequency of this 5ND mode must also be sufficiently separated from this frequency. Ultimately, the deficiency in the current vibration avoidance standards stems from insufficient understanding and inaccurate naming of the vibration modes of disc-like structures. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended in engineering research to use at least the first two diametrical components of the vibration modes for the naming and analysis of natural modes.

Finally, the design of the DBD model used in this paper is made with the idea of having similar mode shapes than real pump-turbine

Fig. 7. Comparison of the diametrical components of the first 3ND mode shape.

runners. Applying the decomposition method explained in [29] to analyze the first 3ND mode shape of a real turbine with seven blades, the following results in Fig. 7 were obtained.

The peripheral deformation of the real structure was obtained by means of experimental modal analysis on the runner. It is clearly seen that the 3ND mode shape also exhibits a strong 4ND component, as well as 10 and 11. In the DBD, the same two components dominate the mode-shape decomposition of the respective mode shape and therefore, it will be used as a simplified model which can explain the same splitting phenomena of the mode shapes that occurs in pump turbines.

3. Analytical analysis of the diametrical components of the structural mode shapes

By comparing the mode shapes of a simple disc and the DBD structure, it has been clarified that the diametrical components are formed under the interference of the blades. This chapter aims to further analyze the mechanism of the formation of these diametrical components and, based on this, predict the mode shape splitting of disc-like structures rotating underwater.

3.1. Mechanisms for the generation of diametrical components

The vibration response of a structure can be regarded as the superposition of all modes. When all the particles move in phase or in antiphase (real mode shape), the deformation of a simple disc can be expressed as [41,42]

$$w(r, \theta, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} W_{nm}(r) \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_{nm}) \cdot \cos(\omega_{nm}t) \quad (7)$$

The deformation of a single mode can be expressed as

$$w(r, \theta, t) = W_{nm}(r) \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_{nm}) \cdot \cos(\omega_{nm}t) \quad (8)$$

where w represents the transverse deformation in the direction perpendicular to the plane of the disc, r is the radial position, θ is the angular position, and t is time. m is the number of nodal circles. W_{nm} is a function involving Bessel functions. It is generally sufficient to analyze the diametrical modes with $m = 0$, which are more likely to be excited. To simplify the subsequent analysis, we omit m from the equation and replace W_{nm} with the amplitude A_n at a specific radial position (for instance at the periphery of the disk), yielding

$$w(\theta, t) = A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \quad (9)$$

From the perspective of vibration propagation, the above mode shape is a standing wave, where the positions of the peaks, troughs, and nodal points are fixed. In reality, this standing wave is formed by the superposition of two counterpropagating traveling waves. In any real mode, the wavelength and intensity of the disturbance propagating simultaneously in two directions along the circumferential direction are equal:

$$\begin{aligned} w(\theta, t) &= A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n + \omega_n t) + \frac{1}{2}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

When the mass or stiffness distribution of a structural system is uneven, the amplitude of the traveling wave will change locally. If the local mass or stiffness increases, the amplitude of the traveling wave will attenuate. Let us introduce an attenuation coefficient $\gamma_n(\theta)$ to describe the change in the amplitude of the traveling wave caused by local variations in mass or stiffness. In this case, the disturbance propagation in both directions along a certain circumference can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} w(\theta, t) &= \frac{1}{2}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n + \omega_n t) \cdot \gamma_n(\theta) + \frac{1}{2}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \gamma_n(\theta) \\ &= A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \cdot \gamma_n(\theta) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In which, the attenuation coefficient $\gamma_n(\theta)$ can be represented by a Fourier series.

$$\gamma_n(\theta) = \gamma_{n,0} + \sum_{i=1} \gamma_{n,i} \cdot \cos(i\theta + \varphi_i) \quad \gamma_{n,0} \in (0, 1), \gamma_{n,i} \in [0, 1] \quad (12)$$

In this case, we analyze the structure with Z_b blades as an example. For the structure, changes in local mass and stiffness are caused by the presence of the blades. It can be observed that when $i = Z_b$, the value of $\gamma_{n,i}$ is most significant. Therefore, $\gamma_n(\theta)$ can be approximated as:

$$\gamma_n(\theta) \approx \gamma_{n,0} + \gamma_{n,Z_b} \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \quad \gamma_{n,Z_b} \in (0, 1) \quad (13)$$

Therefore, equation (11) can be rewritten as

$$w(\theta, t) = \gamma_{n,0}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) + \gamma_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \quad (14)$$

Through trigonometric transformation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \cos[(n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b}] \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \cos[(n + Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n + \varphi_{Z_b}] \cdot \cos(\omega_n t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

This results in two standing waves with diametrical components of $|n - Z_b|$ and $|n + Z_b|$. Similarly, these two standing waves, influenced by the Z_b blades, will generate two more standing waves with diametrical components of $|n - 2Z_b|$ and $|n + 2Z_b|$, and so on. It should be noted that standing waves do not require a distinction of direction, and therefore, the absolute value of the diametrical components can be used to describe them.

The above analysis qualitatively explains the mechanism of the diametrical components' generation, and it is indeed sufficient to support the subsequent research in this paper. However, in the analytical solution, the amplitudes corresponding to the diametrical components $|n - Z_b|$ and $|n + Z_b|$ are equal, which is not fully consistent with the simulation and experimental results. The reason is that the assumption that the wave amplitude is influenced by local mass and stiffness is overly idealized. Therefore, we further refined the attenuation coefficient $\gamma_n(\theta)$. By back-calculating from the experimental results [29] and simulation results, the attenuation coefficient can be written as

$$\gamma_n(\theta) = \gamma_{n,0} + \gamma_{n,Z_b} \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) + \beta_n(\theta) \tag{16}$$

$$\beta_n(\theta) = \beta_{n,Z_b} \cdot \tan(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \quad \beta_{n,Z_b} \in (0, 1) \tag{17}$$

where $\beta_n(\theta)$ is the modified function of the attenuation coefficient. In equation (13), the magnitude of the attenuation coefficient corresponding to each mode is different, but the distribution of the attenuation coefficient along the circumferential direction is consistent. The $\beta_n(\theta)$ term specifically accounts for the coupling effect between n and Z_b .

Substituting equations (16) and (17) into equation (11), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) + \gamma_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \beta_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \sin(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Then, applying the cosine difference formula, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ (\gamma_{n,Z_b} - \beta_{n,Z_b})A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \beta_{n,Z_b}A_n \cdot \cos[(n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b}] \cdot \cos(\omega_n t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Finally, applying the product-to-sum formulas, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0}A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n) \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_{n,Z_b} + \beta_{n,Z_b})A_n \cdot \cos[(n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b}] \cdot \cos(\omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_{n,Z_b} - \beta_{n,Z_b})A_n \cdot \cos[(n + Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n + \varphi_{Z_b}] \cdot \cos(\omega_n t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Fig. 8. Analytical results of modal diametrical components of the DBD structure. (a) Standing wave; (b) Traveling wave.

At this point, the amplitude corresponding to the diametrical component $|n - Z_b|$ is clearly larger than that of $|n + Z_b|$, and the amplitudes of further iterations, such as $|n - 2Z_b|$ and $|n + 2Z_b|$, become smaller. A schematic of this analytical solution is shown in Fig. 8(a), which is consistent with the simulation and experimental results. In fact, the standing waves in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 4 can also be represented by a series of traveling waves, as shown in Fig. 8(b). In practical engineering, the DBD structure (or rather, the runner it represents) rotates. The transmission of vibration signals in the rotor–stator reference frame [29], and the mode splitting phenomenon [22,23], will cause the structural dynamic response to manifest as traveling waves. Therefore, when conducting modal analysis on disc-like structures, it is necessary to decompose their mode shapes into traveling waves for a better understanding.

3.2. Prediction of mode shape splitting

Presas et al. [24,32] and Louyot et al. [26] have fully demonstrated that when a disc rotates in a heavy fluid, in the rotating reference frame, any diametrical mode will split from its original standing wave (i.e., real mode shape) into two independent traveling wave modes with different frequencies and damping, moving in opposite directions. The fundamental cause of this is that the two opposite traveling waves experience different added mass due to the relative rotational speed with respect to the water. Therefore, it can be anticipated that when the DBD structure rotates in a heavy fluid, it will undergo mode splitting, similar to the simple disc, resulting in two independent traveling wave modes. However, unlike the simple disc, each diametrical mode of the structure or runner contains a series of traveling wave components, as shown in Fig. 8(b). When it splits into two independent traveling wave modes, it remains unknown which components will be included in each mode. Therefore, it is necessary to further predict the splitting rules of the mode shapes of the structure.

To address this, we can analyze which traveling wave components are accompanied by a single traveling wave under the interference of the blades. Taking the forward traveling wave as an example, the propagation of a disturbance on a particular circumference of a simple disc can be written as

$$w(\theta, t) = A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \quad (21)$$

When performing analytical analysis of traveling waves, the direction must be distinguished. First, define the rotational direction of the simple disc and the DBD structure as the positive direction. Therefore, in the expression $\cos(n\theta - \omega_n t)$, $n > 0$ represents a forward traveling wave, and $n < 0$ represents a backward traveling wave.

Under the interference of the blades, this forward traveling wave becomes

$$w(\theta, t) = A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \gamma_n(\theta) \quad (22)$$

At this point, the modified function $\beta_n(\theta)$ of the attenuation coefficient shown in Equation (17) also needs to rotate along with the waveform, which means adding the $\omega_n t$ term:

$$\beta_n(\theta) = \beta_{n,Z_b} \cdot \tan(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \quad (23)$$

By substituting Equations (16) and (23) into Equation (22) (alternatively, using the unmodified attenuation coefficient as shown in Equation (12) does not affect the conclusions of this section), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0} A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \\ &+ \gamma_{n,Z_b} A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \\ &+ \beta_{n,Z_b} A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \tan(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

In which,

$$\begin{aligned} \tan(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) &= \frac{\sin(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \sin(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b})}{\cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t)} \\ &= \frac{\cos[(n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b} - \omega_n t] - \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b})}{\cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t)} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Therefore, Equation (24) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0} A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \\ &+ \left(\gamma_{n,Z_b} - \beta_{n,Z_b} \right) A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \cdot \cos(Z_b\theta + \varphi_{Z_b}) \\ &+ \beta_{n,Z_b} A_n \cdot \cos[(n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b} - \omega_n t] \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Through trigonometric transformation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(\theta, t) &= \gamma_{n,0} A_n \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n - \omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} (\gamma_{n,Z_b} + \beta_{n,Z_b}) A_n \cdot \cos((n - Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n - \varphi_{Z_b} - \omega_n t) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} (\gamma_{n,Z_b} - \beta_{n,Z_b}) A_n \cdot \cos((n + Z_b)\theta + \varphi_n + \varphi_{Z_b} - \omega_n t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

In this case, the n ND forward traveling wave, influenced by Z_b blades, forms a series of traveling wave components with a diametrical spacing of Z_b , as shown in Fig. 9. Therefore, when the DBD structure rotates in water, the mode splitting will not result in a “forward traveling wave mode” and a “backward traveling wave mode” as with a simple disc. Instead, it will split into two complex traveling wave modes, each containing both forward and backward traveling wave components. Furthermore, in each of the split modes, the interval of the diametrical numbers of the traveling wave components is Z_b .

The above results form the basis for predicting the mode frequency splitting and damping splitting of the DBD structure or runner. Furthermore, it explains the fundamental cause of the multi-frequency vibration observed on the stationary components of hydraulic machinery in real cases, where the frequencies are spaced by integer multiples of the blade passing frequency (see Fig. 1), a phenomenon which will be discussed in detail in Chapter 5.

4. Numerical simulation of mode splitting in the disc-blades-disc structure

Based on the numerical modal analysis of the non-rotating structure and the analytical investigation of the mode shape splitting of the rotating structure, this chapter applies the imposed modal motion method to study the modal frequency and damping splitting of the submerged rotating structure.

4.1. Imposed modal motion approach

The general procedure for predicting the inherent modal parameters of submerged structures using the imposed modal motion method involves introducing a mode shape at the boundary of the CFD model, and inducing periodic vibration based on an approximate natural frequency, which is then used to extract the hydrodynamic coefficients. This simulation method has been widely applied in the prediction of hydraulic damping [31,43,44]. Using this method, the energy dissipated (modal power) by a given mode shape during one vibration cycle can be obtained. The ratio of modal power to the total system energy defines the hydraulic damping ratio. A detailed process can be found in reference [31].

Building upon the aforementioned concept, Nennemann et al. [45] proposed a method for calculating the added mass, which laid the foundation for predicting the modal frequency splitting of submerged rotating components. To determine the added mass coefficient for a specific mode, the modal force needs to be extracted. The modal force at a certain moment in the CFD model can be obtained either through the surface integral of the scalar product between force and modal shape or by summing the scalar product between nodal forces and modal shapes:

$$F_{m,CFD} = \int_A (pe + \tau) \cdot \bar{u}(r, \theta) dA = \sum F_i \cdot \bar{u}(r, \theta) \tag{28}$$

here, p is the wall pressure; e is the axial unit vector; τ is the axial shear force component; F_i is the axial total force at node i ; $\bar{u}(r, \theta)$ is the normalized axial displacement.

According to the equation of motion for a single-degree-of-freedom oscillation, the dynamic behavior of the disc can be expressed as:

$$F_m(t) = (M_s + M_w + M_f) \ddot{u}_r + (C_s + C_w + C_f) \dot{u}_r + (K_s + K_w + K_f) u_r \tag{29}$$

Where M , C , and K represent modal mass, modal damping, and modal stiffness, respectively; subscripts s , w , and f stand for structure, static water, and flow effects; u_r is the reference displacement. The modal force in the CFD model includes additional mass, damping,

Fig. 9. Wave components in a specific traveling wave mode of the rotating DBD structure in water.

and stiffness contributions from static water and flow effects.

$$F_{m,CFD}(t) = M_{wf}\ddot{u}_r + C_{wf}\dot{u}_r + K_{wf}u_r \tag{30}$$

According to the particular solution of the forced harmonic oscillator's differential equation, $u_r(t) = u_m \cos(\omega t - \varphi)$, we can obtain:

$$F_{m,CFD} = \sqrt{(K_{wf}u_m - M_{wf}u_m\omega^2)^2 + (C_{wf}u_m\omega)^2} \tag{31}$$

where u_m is the amplitude of the imposed mode applied to the CFD model; ω is the frequency of the mode; φ is the phase between the forced vibration and the response; $F_{m,CFD}$ has different meanings in different situations. When the imposed mode is a standing wave, it refers to the amplitude of the modal force, and when the mode is a traveling wave, it refers to the modal force at any instantaneous moment.

Given that the added stiffness provided by the fluid is small, for simplicity in solving, the K_{wf} term can be ignored. And the added damping can be calculated through modal work:

$$C_{wf} = \frac{1}{H} \sum_{j=1}^H \frac{-W_{m,j}}{\pi\omega u_m^2} \tag{32}$$

where H is the number of oscillation cycles, and $W_{m,j}$ is the modal work during the j th cycle. Then, the damping ratio can be obtained:

$$\zeta = \frac{C_{wf}}{2\omega(M_s + M_w)} \tag{33}$$

The calculation of modal work is similar to that of modal force:

$$W_{m,j} = \int_{(j-1)T}^{jT} \int_A (pn + \tau) \cdot \dot{u}_r dAdt \tag{34}$$

Combining equations (34), (32), and the equation (31) with the removal of the K_{wf} term, the added mass M_{wf} can be calculated [45]:

$$M_{wf} = \frac{\sqrt{F_{m,CFD}^2 - (C_{wf}u_m\omega)^2}}{u_m\omega^2} \tag{35}$$

Then, the natural frequency of the rotating disc in water is given by:

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_s}{M_s + M_{wf}}} \tag{36}$$

where K_s and M_s can be obtained from finite element results [46].

Another key point in using the imposed modal motion method to predict the modal parameters of submerged rotating structures is the application of the mode shape to the CFD model. For a simple disc, the loading can be directly performed according to the following equation

$$w(r, \theta, t) = \frac{1}{2}W_n(r) \cdot \cos(n\theta + \varphi_n \pm \omega_{n-FEM}t) \tag{37}$$

In which, $W_n(r)$, φ_n , and ω_{n-FEM} are obtained through FEM analysis. Among them, $W_n(r)$ and φ_n can be taken from results either in air or water, while ω_{n-FEM} must be based on the results in water.

With reference to the above equation, the standing wave mode and a specific traveling wave mode of the DBD structure can be written as follows

$$w(r, \theta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z)] \cdot \cos(\omega_{n-FEM}t) \tag{38}$$

$$w(r, \theta, z, t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z) \pm \omega_{n-FEM}t] \tag{39}$$

In which, the frequency corresponding to each diametrical component is consistent, but $W_n(r, z)$ and $\varphi_n(r, z)$ may differ. It is difficult to decompose each diametrical component's $W_n(r, z)$ and $\varphi_n(r, z)$ from the FEM results, especially at the locations of the blades. Therefore, this approach cannot be used for loading directly.

Let's adopt an alternative approach. First, we combine the $W_n(r, z)$ term and the $\cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z)]$ term from equation (38), and obtain the amplitude at all nodes of this standing wave mode:

$$A_{\text{Std}}(r, \theta, z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z)] \tag{40}$$

Since the standing wave mode is composed of the superposition of two counterpropagating traveling wave modes, there must be corresponding $A_{\text{Trvl}}(r, z, \theta)$ and $\varphi_0(r, z, \theta)$ that satisfy

$$A_{\text{Std}}(r, \theta, z) = 2A_{\text{Trvl}}(r, \theta, z) \cdot \cos[\varphi_0(r, \theta, z)] \tag{41}$$

where $A_{\text{Trvl}}(r, z, \theta)$ is the amplitude of an individual traveling wave mode, and $\varphi_0(r, z, \theta)$ is used to represent the initial phase of the mode. At this point, a specific traveling wave mode of the DBD structure can be expressed as

$$w(r, \theta, t) = A_{\text{Trvl}}(r, \theta, z) \cdot \cos[\varphi_0(r, \theta, z) \pm \omega_{n-\text{FEM}}] \tag{42}$$

In commonly used commercial software (ANSYS®, MSC NASTRAN®), it is restricted to analyze the natural frequencies of rotating DBD structures from a stationary reference frame [29]. This is because each diametrical mode of the structure corresponds to multiple frequencies in the stationary reference frame. However, in this study, when performing modal analysis of a rotating structure in air using ANSYS®, it was found that a series of paired traveling wave modes could be obtained in the stationary reference frame, and the traveling wave components in each mode match those in equation (27). Therefore, through this method, the values of $A_{\text{Trvl}}(r, z, \theta)$ and $\varphi_0(r, z, \theta)$ can be obtained, which can then be used in equation (42) to load the traveling wave mode shapes into the CFD model.

4.2. Numerical model

The CFD model shown in Fig. 10 was constructed. The computational domain primarily used structured hexahedral meshes for discretization, with refinement near the walls. In the commercial software ANSYS CFX®, the entire computational domain was defined as a rotating domain, with all boundaries set as no-slip walls. The external boundaries of the domain were given a reverse rotational velocity of the same magnitude. In the rotating reference frame, the surface of the structure undergoes periodic motion according to a specific traveling wave mode. Before this, steady-state calculations were performed under undisturbed conditions to serve as the initial conditions for the unsteady analysis. Pressure measurement points were set at 36 locations in both the rotating and stationary reference frames, as shown in Fig. 10(a) with P_{ri} and P_{si} .

A second-order backward Euler transient scheme and a high-resolution advection scheme were used for the unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) calculations. The $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, known for its good numerical robustness, was employed in the turbulence modeling. For this turbulence model, the grid adhered to the condition of $y^+ > 30$. This coarse grid was sufficient for the impost modal motion simulation in this study, as frequency splitting is a non-viscous flow phenomenon and is therefore not affected by the viscous effects in the boundary layer [26].

A sensitivity analysis was conducted on the mesh size, time step, and vibration amplitude. Ultimately, a mesh configuration with 2,700,572 elements was selected as the reference setup for all models, with a time step of $\Delta t = 1/360f_n$, and a vibration amplitude of $u_m = 0.1$ mm for the structure.

4.3. Results and Discussion

In previous studies [32], the above method was used to simulate the mode frequency splitting of a simple disc, with results that closely matched experimental data. Building on this, this chapter selects the 2ND-IP mode, 2ND-CP mode, 3ND-IP mode, and 3ND-CP mode of the structure for numerical simulation analysis.

According to the analyses in Chapters 2 and 3, when the structure rotates in water, a 2ND mode will split into a wave mode primarily containing diametrical components +2 and –5, and another wave mode mainly containing diametrical components –2 and +5. Similarly, a 3ND mode will split into a wave mode primarily containing diametrical components +3 and –4, and another wave mode mainly containing diametrical components –3 and +4. Here, the symbols “+” and “-” represent the wave components moving in

Fig. 10. Schematic diagram of the CFD model. (a) three-dimensional model of the fluid domain for unsteady calculations; (b) reference scheme for computational grid.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 11. Variation of natural frequency and hydraulic damping with rotational speed for each mode of the submerged rotating DBD structure. (Observation from the rotating reference frame) (a) 2ND-IP mode; (b) 3ND-IP mode; (c) 3ND-CP mode; (d) 2ND-CP mode.

the same or opposite direction as the DBD structure, respectively.

The natural frequencies and hydraulic damping of these traveling wave modes as a function of the structure’s rotational speed are shown in Fig. 11. The results indicate that the trend of natural frequency and hydraulic damping with speed variation for the IP modes is similar to that of a simple disc [27,32]. For the traveling wave mode with the main diametrical component in the positive direction, the natural frequency decreases with increasing rotational speed, while hydraulic damping increases with rotational speed. Conversely, for the traveling wave mode with the main diametrical component in the negative direction, the natural frequency increases with rotational speed. Hydraulic damping also increases with rotational speed, but at a slower rate compared to another mode. Unlike the IP mode, the two traveling wave modes resulting from the splitting of the CP mode show very similar natural frequencies and hydraulic damping, without exhibiting the pronounced “splitting” effect. Specifically, the natural frequency slightly decreases with increasing rotational speed, while hydraulic damping increases with speed. It is important to note that since the DBD structure in this study is enclosed in a casing with no mean flow during rotation, the results may differ from those of actual rotating runners.

5. Resonance characteristics of the submerged rotating DBD structure from the stationary reference frame

In the previous sections, the analysis of the modal vibration signals of rotating structures was conducted in the rotating reference frame. However, in real applications, pressure, vibrations, and noise sensors are typically located on stationary components due to the physical complexity of installing them in a submerged and rotating structure. Therefore, it is necessary to further discuss the transmission of vibrations from the rotating reference frame to the stationary reference frame. This chapter first analyzes the modal vibration characteristics of the DBD structure as observed from the stationary reference frame using analytical methods. Then, the characteristics of pressure fluctuations induced by the disc vibration are analyzed using CFD methods. Finally, the vibrations induced in the stationary components by the disc vibrations are solved using FEM methods.

5.1. Analytical analysis of modal vibration signal transmission from the rotating reference frame to the stationary reference frame

When the structure rotates at low speed in air, the gyroscopic effect, centrifugal force, and air flow on the dynamic characteristics can be neglected. In this case, the vibration mode of the structure observed from the rotating reference frame can be expressed as

$$w_{rot}(r, \theta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z)] \cdot \cos(\omega_{n,rot}t) \tag{43}$$

If analyzed from the stationary reference frame, the angular coordinate θ can be replaced by $\beta = \theta + \Omega t$, yielding:

$$w_{stat}(r, \beta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n(\beta - \Omega t) + \varphi_n(r, z)] \cdot \cos(\omega_{n,rot}t) \tag{44}$$

Through trigonometric transformation, the above equation can be rewritten as:

$$w_{stat}(r, \beta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{W_n(r, z)}{2} \cdot \cos[(\omega_{n,rot} + n\Omega)t - \varphi_n(r, z) - n\beta] + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{W_n(r, z)}{2} \cdot \cos[(\omega_{n,rot} - n\Omega)t + \varphi_n(r, z) + n\beta] \tag{45}$$

It can be concluded that when the rotating DBD structure vibrates in a certain diametrical mode in air, multiple pairs of counter-propagating traveling waves with frequencies $\omega_{n,rot} + n\Omega$ and $\omega_{n,rot} - n\Omega$ can be observed in the stationary reference frame, as shown in Fig. 12. This phenomenon was experimentally verified by Presas et al. in [29].

Fig. 12. Modal vibration frequencies of a rotating DBD structure in air observed in the stationary reference frame. (Example with the 3ND-IP mode).

Fig. 13. Modal vibration frequencies of the underwater rotating DBD structure observed in the stationary reference frame. (a) 2ND-IP mode; (b) 3ND-IP mode; (c) 3ND-CP mode; (d) 2ND-CP mode.

When the structure rotates in water, its diametrical modes split into two independent traveling wave modes. At this point, the mode of the structure observed from the rotating reference frame can be expressed as

$$w_{rot}(r, \theta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\theta + \varphi_n(r, z) \pm \omega_{n,rot}t] \tag{46}$$

If analyzed from the stationary reference frame, the angular coordinate θ is replaced by β , and the expression becomes

$$w_{stat}(r, \beta, z, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} W_n(r, z) \cdot \cos[n\beta + \varphi_n(r, z) + (\pm \omega_{n,rot} - n\Omega)t] \tag{47}$$

Therefore, multiple simultaneously existing traveling wave components with different frequencies will be observed for each mode. The frequency of the forward traveling wave components is $\omega_{n,rot} + n\Omega$, while the frequency of the backward traveling wave components is $\omega_{n,rot} - n\Omega$. By combining Equation (27), the results in Fig. 5, and those in Fig. 11, the frequency-domain signal of the

Fig. 14. Pressure pulsations at rotating and stationary measurement points. (a) Travelling wave mode formed by the components 3- and 4+ excited; (b) Travelling wave mode formed by the components 3+ and 4- excited.

structure’s modes in the stationary reference frame can be predicted. When $f_N = 5$ Hz, the frequency-domain signal is shown in Fig. 13. The results indicate that, when the structure rotates in water, regardless of which mode is excited, the vibration observed in the stationary reference frame always exhibits multi-frequency characteristics, with a frequency spacing of $Z_b f_N$ between each frequency.

5.2. Numerical simulation of pressure pulsations induced by DBD vibrations

Based on the CFD model constructed in Section 4.2, numerical simulations are carried out to analyze the characteristics of pressure pulsations in the stationary reference frame induced by the vibrating rotating DBD structure. The modal frequencies in equation (42) are modified according to the predicted results from Section 4.3. The distribution of pressure measurement points is shown in Fig. 10 (a).

Taking the 3ND-IP mode as an example, when one of the independent travelling wave modes formed after its splitting is excited, the pressure pulsations at some measurement points are shown in Fig. 14. The results indicate that the pressure pulsation frequency components at each rotating measurement point are relatively singular, with varying amplitudes. At the stationary measurement points, the pressure pulsations mainly contain two frequency components, with nearly identical amplitudes corresponding to a particular frequency component at each point. Moreover, the frequencies of the pressure pulsations in the stationary reference frame obtained from CFD simulations are consistent with the structure vibration frequencies obtained from analytical analysis. This indicates that, in practical engineering, some of the pressure pulsation frequencies measured may reflect the vibrations of the rotating components in the stationary frame.

The pressure pulsation signals at all measurement points in both the rotating and stationary reference frames were subjected to FFT analysis. Based on the obtained frequencies, amplitudes, and phases, the pressure field mode shapes corresponding to the dominant and secondary frequencies were plotted, as shown in Fig. 15. It can be observed that the pressure field mode shapes corresponding to the dominant frequencies of 149.40 Hz and 142.60 Hz in the rotating reference frame appear as composite waves. While in the stationary reference frame, the pressure field mode shapes corresponding to the dominant and secondary frequencies are simple sine waves. Furthermore, the pressure field mode shapes for each dominant and secondary frequency match the individual travelling wave components in the mode shapes of the structure. This result provides theoretical support for the multi-frequency vibration phenomena observed in real cases (see again Fig. 1).

Fig. 15. Pressure field mode shapes corresponding to each dominant frequency in the rotating and stationary reference frames. (a) Travelling wave mode formed by the components 3- and 4+ excited; (b) Travelling wave mode formed by the components 3+ and 4- excited.

5.3. Dynamic response of the casing induced by DBD vibration

For the casing shown in Fig. 1(c), a transient structural dynamics finite element model was constructed in ANSYS®. The solution was carried out in two steps. The first step consisted of 5 substeps, each with a time interval of 1 s. The second step included 1440 substeps, with each substep having a time interval of (1/36/149.40) s. The damping ratio corresponding to the first natural frequency of the casing, 338.64 Hz, was set to 0.05. The computational domain was discretised using high-order solid elements Solid186. Due to lower precision requirements in this section, a mesh with a total of 272,425 nodes was selected for numerical simulation. Finally, the wall pressure corresponding to the case in Fig. 14(a) was converted and applied to the inner wall of the casing. Since the entire computational domain in the CFD model is rotating, the exported wall pressure is in the rotating reference frame, necessitating a coordinate transformation. Additionally, to clearly display the vibration shape of the casing in the displacement contour plots, the time-averaged value of the pressure pulsation was adjusted to zero.

The axial displacement contour of the casing is shown in Fig. 16(a). It is visually evident that the dominant diametrical component of the casing's vibration is 3. The axial displacement at the marked measurement point in Fig. 16(a) was extracted and displayed in Fig. 16(b). The vibration signal at this measurement point revealed two frequencies: 134.46 Hz as the dominant frequency and 168.07 Hz as the secondary frequency. This result closely aligns with the outcomes observed in the stationary reference frame shown in Fig. 13(b). However, compared to the DBD structure, the dominant frequency amplitude ratio on the casing is significantly higher.

To further decompose the vibration shape of the casing, a series of additional displacement measurement points were set along the circumference where the original measurement point was located, and an ODS analysis was conducted. The results were highly consistent with those in Fig. 15(a). The vibration shape corresponding to 134.46 Hz is a 3ND backward traveling wave, while 168.07 Hz corresponds to a 4ND forward traveling wave. Due to the high redundancy, these results are not presented again.

Overall, the vibration characteristics of the casing are consistent with both the pressure pulsations and the DBD structure's vibrations. This consistency is partly supported by the modal experiments conducted by Weder et al. [47] on a rotating disc and an adjacent stationary disc.

In a pump-turbine prototype, the number of pressure measurement points in the head cover is usually limited, making it difficult to obtain the mode shapes of the pressure field through direct measurements. Nevertheless, as we have shown in this paper, it would be sufficient to analyze the multi-frequency vibration pattern to deduce the resonant mode that may be triggered in the pump-turbine runner.

For example, taking the pumped storage unit mentioned in the introduction (Fig. 1), the 150.7 Hz component in the vibration signal of the top cover corresponds to a 4ND backward traveling wave, while the 200.7 Hz component corresponds to a 5ND forward traveling wave. According to Equation (47), the vibration frequency of the runner in the rotating reference frame is 172.9 Hz. Therefore, for that case we conclude that the resonant frequency was 172.9 Hz and the mode-shape was a traveling wave mode composed of a 4ND backward wave and a 5ND forward wave (runner with 9 blades).

6. Conclusion

This study presents new insights into the resonance mechanism of pump-turbine runners and addresses a long-standing challenge in predicting and diagnosing runner resonance faults based on measurements from stationary-frame sensors. The main contributions include: (1) Identifying and correcting limitations in the current understanding of the mode shapes of pump-turbine runners; (2) Proposing and validating that a disc-blades-disc (DBD) structure, when rotating in water, undergoes mode splitting similar to that observed in a simple disc; (3) Revealing the mechanism behind recently observed high-vibration phenomena with complex multi-frequency characteristics on the top cover of real pump-turbine units. The findings of this study are relevant for preventing high vibrations in pump turbine runners and avoiding premature failures.

Specifically, by employing a combination of analytical methods, finite element methods, and the imposed modal motion method based on computational fluid dynamics, the inherent modal characteristics of DBD structures, particularly the diametrical components and their formation mechanisms, are explored. It is shown that the analyzed DBD structure has similar mode shape characteristics than real pump turbines with the same number of blades. The modal shape splitting rules for underwater rotating DBD structures are analyzed, and the splitting characteristics of the natural frequency and hydraulic damping are predicted. The manifestation of resonance in rotating components in a stationary reference frame is also discussed. The following conclusions are drawn:

- For a DBD structure with Z_b blades, if a particular mode contains the diametrical component n , it will must also include diametrical components $|n - Z_b|$ and $|n + Z_b|$. These are called secondary diametrical components which for some specific modes, they can have a similar amplitude than the principal component. Therefore, when assessing the potentiality of exciting a resonance in a pump turbine runner it is recommended to compare at least the two main diametrical components of every structural mode shape with the rotor-stator-interaction pattern.
- The attenuation coefficient $\gamma_n(\theta)$ can be used to describe the impact of local changes in mass and stiffness on the amplitude distribution of the travelling wave modes, allowing for the prediction of diametrical components in the DBD structure's natural modes through analytical methods and determining the modal shape splitting rules. When the structure rotates underwater, its diametrical mode splits into two independent travelling wave modes, with each mode containing multiple diametrical components (i.e., travelling wave components), and the difference between the diametrical components within a particular mode is equal to the number of blades Z_b .

Fig. 16. Dynamic response simulation results of the casing. (the DBD structure vibrates in the 3ND-IP (3-, 4+) traveling wave mode) (a) Displacement contour at a specific moment; (b) Vibration signal at the displacement measurement point.

- Building on the numerical prediction of mode frequency splitting in a simple disc [32,45], a method is proposed to load the travelling wave mode of the DBD structure into the fluid modelled by means of CFD, successfully applying the imposed modal motion approach to the structure. The results show that the natural frequency and hydraulic damping of the in-phase mode (IP) vary with the rotational speed in a manner similar to that of a simple disc [27,32], with a clear “splitting” phenomenon observed. In contrast, the two travelling wave modes generated by the splitting of the CP mode have very similar natural frequencies and hydraulic damping, without exhibiting a noticeable “splitting” effect.
- When observing the resonance of a given mode-shape of the DBD structure from the stationary reference frame, a “multi-frequency” characteristic will be observed with a frequency difference being a multiple of the blade number and rotational frequency. This “multi-frequency” characteristic, which is a manifestation of the resonance on the rotating frame will be seen by vibration sensors and pressure sensors placed on the stationary frame.
- Finally, it is worth mentioning that the conclusions are specifically drawn for pump-turbine runners and high-head centrifugal pumps, which are generally disk-like structures with relatively few blades compared to Francis runners. When measuring the resonance characteristics of other types of runners, namely Francis and Kaplan, using sensors on the stationary frame, they may exhibit different frequency characteristics, as recent papers have shown [48,49].

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xiang Xia: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Alexandre Presas:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Greco Moraga:** Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Lingjiu Zhou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Resources. **Wei Wang:** Formal analysis, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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